

Managing gene flow: A prerequisite for recombinant DNA biotechnology

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A humble offering, placed at the Lotus Feet of

Bhagavan Sri Sathya Sai Baba

and so,

*it is with love and servitude that I dedicate this research to the many
subsistence farmers of Africa. You are the ancient foundation of our
continent and this research was performed with a fervent hope of
enlightenment and as a modest attempt to lighten some of your plight.*

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